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The spectrum of antimicrobial activity of Gelomyrtol[®] capsules

Domina Petric, MD

ABSTRACT

Gelomyrtol[®] Forte capsules (Medis Adria) are indicated in the treatment of acute and chronic bronchitis and sinusitis for children older than 6 years and adults.

Considering the wide spectrum of antimicrobial and antioxidant activity of Gelomyrtol[®] Forte capsules (mixture of purified essential oils of eucalyptus, sweet orange, myrtle and lemon) along with secretolytic and secretomotor activity it might be used as additional therapeutic agent in COVID-19 pneumonia with or without bacterial superinfection.

INTRODUCTION

Gelomyrtol[®] Forte capsules (Medis Adria) are indicated in the treatment of acute and chronic bronchitis and sinusitis for children older than 6 years and adults. Gelomyrtol[®] capsules have secretolytic and secretomotor effect.

The active substance is a distillate of a mixture of purified essential oils of eucalyptus, sweet orange, myrtle and lemon.

Each capsule contains 300 mg of a distillate mixture of *Eucalyptus globulus Labill.*, *aetheroleum rectificatum* (purified eucalyptus essential oil), *Citrus sinensis (L.) Osbeck*, *aetheroleum rectificatum* (purified sweet orange essential oil), *Citrus lemon (L.) Burman fil.*, *aetheroleum rectificatum* (purified lemon essential oil) and *Myrtus communis L.*, *aetheroleum rectificatum* (purified myrtle essential oil) (66:32:1:1 m/m).

Dose for children aged 6-12 years is 1 capsule 1-3 times a day in acute inflammatory conditions and 1 capsule 1-2 times a day in chronic inflammatory conditions. Dose for children older than 12 years and adults is 1 capsule 3-4 times a

day in acute inflammatory conditions and 1 capsule 2-3 times a day in chronic inflammatory conditions.

Side effects are rare: nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, hypersensitivity reactions¹.

EUCALYPTUS ESSENTIAL OIL

In the study conducted by Mulyaningsih and coworkers (2011) authors found that EGF (fruit oil of *Eucalyptus globulus*) exerted the most pronounced activity against methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MIC ~ 250 µg/ml). EGF mainly consisted of aromadendrene (31.17%), whereas ECL (*E. citriodora* Hook) had citronellal (90.07%) and citronellol (4.32%) as the major compounds. 1,8-cineole was most abundant in EGL (leaf oils of *E. globulus*, 86.51%) and ERL (*E. radiata* Sieber ex DC, 82.66%)².

In the study conducted by Bachir and Benali (2012) authors concluded that essential oil of the leaves of *E. globulus* has antimicrobial activity against gram negative bacteria (*E. coli*) as well as gram positive bacteria (*S. aureus*)³.

Brachot and coworkers (2017) showed in the study that two unique blends of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum*, *Daucus carota*, *Eucalyptus globulus* and

Rosmarinus officinalis essential oils (AB1 and AB2; cinnamon EOs from two different suppliers) were active against the fourteen Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria strains tested, including some antibiotic-resistant strains. Blend AB1 was also effective against H1N1 and HSV1 viruses. With this dual activity, against H1N1 and against *S. aureus* and *S. pneumoniae*, AB1 may be interesting to treat influenza and post-influenza bacterial pneumonia infections⁴.

One study (2020) showed that the calculated parameters such as RMSD, binding energy, and binding site similarity indicated effective binding of eucalyptol to COVID-19 proteinase. Active site prediction further validated the role of active site residues in ligand binding. PIC results indicated that, Mpro protein of COVID-19/eucalyptol complexes forms hydrophobic interactions, hydrogen bond interactions and strong ionic interactions. Authors concluded that eucalyptol may represent potential treatment potential to act as COVID-19 Mpro inhibitor⁵.

In another study the activity of *Eucalyptus globulus* essential oil was determined for 120 isolates of *Streptococcus pyogenes*, 20 isolates of *S. pneumoniae*, 40 isolates of *S. agalactiae*, 20 isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus*, 40 isolates of *Haemophilus influenzae*, 30 isolates of *H.*

parainfluenzae, 10 isolates of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, 10 isolates of *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* and two viruses, a strain of adenovirus and a strain of mumps virus, all obtained from clinical specimens of patients with respiratory tract infections. The cytotoxicity was evaluated on VERO cells by the MTT test. The antibacterial activity was evaluated by the Kirby Bauer paper method, minimum inhibitory concentration, and minimum bactericidal concentration. *H. influenzae*, *parainfluenzae*, and *S. maltophilia* were the most susceptible, followed by *S. pneumoniae*. The antiviral activity, assessed by means of virus yield experiments titrated by the end-point dilution method for adenovirus, and by plaque reduction assay for mumps virus, disclosed only a mild activity on mumps virus⁶.

SWEET ORANGE ESSENTIAL OIL

In the study conducted by Frassinetti and coworkers (2011) the antibacterial and antioxidant activities of essential oils from Bitter orange, Sweet orange, Lemon and Mandarin were investigated. The antimicrobial capability of these oils was determined against ten strains of Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria, including some phytopathogenic strains.

All oils showed good antibacterial activity against both Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria. The MICs for selected oils ranged 15–250 µg/mL. The lowest MICs were 15 µg/mL and 20 µg/mL against *Xanthomonas citri* strains. The antioxidant and antiradical scavenging properties of the selected oils were tested by means of 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) assay. All examined oils exhibited a free radical scavenging activity, ranging 20–70% of DPPH inhibition. Lemon oil showed the most antioxidant capacity, with DPPH inhibition rate of 70%⁷.

In another study seven citrus essential oils were screened by disc diffusion assay for their antibacterial act against 11 serotypes/strains of *Salmonella*. The 3 most active oils were selected to determine the minimal inhibitory concentration against the same *Salmonella*. Orange terpenes, single-folded d-limonene, and orange essence terpenes all exhibited inhibitory activity against the *Salmonella spp.* on the disc diffusion assay⁸.

In the study (Geraci et al), the orange peel of 12 cultivars of *Citrus sinensis* from central-eastern Sicily was employed to obtain essential oils and extracts. The ones were extracted through steam distillation, the others through extraction in hexane. Chemical constituents were evaluated in terms of qualitative and quantitative

analyses by gas chromatography/mass spectrometry. Fifty-four components were identified in the steam essential oils and 44 in the extracts. In all the cultivars, the main component is d-limonene (73.9-97%); discrete percentages of linalool, geraniol and nerol were also found. Cluster analysis based on essential oils composition showed a certain degree of affinity between cultivars of the same type. The antimicrobial activity was investigated against three micro-organisms (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*). 'Sanguinello' and 'Solarino Moro' essential oils are significantly active against *L. monocytogenes*, while 'Valencia' hexanic extract against all the tested micro-organisms⁹.

LEMON ESSENTIAL OIL

In the study (Man et al) frankincense, myrtle, thyme, lemon, oregano and lavender essential oils were tested against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Both micellar and aqueous extracts were used for determination of their minimal inhibitory and bactericidal concentrations. The most active oils were oregano, thyme, lemon and lavender, while

the least active were frankincense and myrtle¹⁰.

In another study, antibacterial activity of finger citron essential oil (FCEO, *Citrus medica L. var. sarcodactylis*) and its mechanism against food-borne bacteria were evaluated. A total of 28 components in the oil were identified by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry, in which limonene (45.36%), γ -terpinene (21.23%), and dodecanoic acid (7.52%) were three main components. For *in vitro* antibacterial tests, FCEO exhibited moderately antibacterial activity against common food-borne bacteria: *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Micrococcus luteus*. It showed a better bactericidal effect on Gram-positive bacteria than Gram-negative¹¹.

In the study conducted by Hsouna and coworkers (2017) authors suggested that the *Citrus lemon* essential oil may be a new potential source as natural antimicrobial and antioxidant agents applied in food systems and pharmaceutical industry¹².

MYRTLE ESSENTIAL OIL

One study showed that products with valuable antibacterial activity can be produced from leaves of *Myrtus communis* against *Erysipelothrix rhusiopathiae* (gram positive bacteria that causes erysipeloid in humans¹³).

Many studies have demonstrated *in vitro* antimicrobial and antioxidant effectiveness of *Myrtus communis* L. extracts and essential oils, which is in agreement with current trends. Myrtle seems to be a promising plant regarding alternative antimicrobials against increasing numbers of pathogenic microorganisms resistant to conventional antibiotic and antioxidants which should replace the synthetic ones¹⁴.

Due to synergistic phenomena, the complex mixture of essential oils usually shows a higher antiviral activity than individual compounds¹⁵.

Several phytochemicals have complementary and overlapping inhibition of viral nucleic acid synthesis or inhibition of other stages in viral multiplication¹⁶.

The best known antiviral compound produced by many plants belonging to various families, including *Myrtus communis* L. plant, is α -caryophyllene¹⁵.

CONCLUSION

Considering the wide spectrum of antimicrobial and antioxidant activity of Gelomyrtol[®] Forte capsules (mixture of purified essential oils of eucalyptus, sweet orange, myrtle and lemon) along with secretolytic and secretomotor activity it might be used as additional therapeutic agent in COVID-19 pneumonia with or without bacterial superinfection.

This is not a sponsored article. I do not have conflicts of interest.

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